

The Effect of Nitric Oxide and the Cumulus Cells on the Percentage of In Vitro Maturation (IVM) of Buffalos Normal Ovaries Oocytes

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Abstract

This study was conducted in the laboratory of graduate studies in the Department of Animal Production / College of Agriculture University of AL-Muthanna and the laboratories of the of Jabir Ibn Hayyan Medical University during the period 22/9/2022 to 1/10/2023. The immature oocytes were subjected to the experiment for in vitro maturation (IVM) using the culture medium Dulbeccos Modified Eagles Medium (DMEM) treated with the nitric oxide with two concentrations: the low concentration was (3mM) and the high concentration was (5mM), to determine the effect of the cystic ovaries (follicular and luteal), the presence of cumulus oophorus and the concentration of nitric oxide in the percentage of (IVM) of buffalo oocytes. The result showed that the follicular cystic ovaries recorded the highest concentration of the insulin hormone (28.61 ± 0.15 U/mL) as compared with the luteal cystic ovaries (23.6 ± 0.29 U/mL) and the normal ovaries (24.41 ± 0.14 U/mL). On the other hand, the normal ovaries recorded a highest concentration of LH (1.003 ± 0.028 U/ml) as compared with the follicular cystic ovaries (0.596 ± 0.02 IU/ml) and the luteal cystic ovaries (0.516 ± 0.2 IU/ml). The luteal cystic ovaries showed the highest concentration of the prolactin hormone (1.050 ± 0.03 ng/ml) as compared with the follicular cystic ovaries (0.883 ± 0.03 ng/ml) and the normal ovaries (0.600 ± 0.02 ng/ml).

Keywords: *nitric oxide, cumulus cells, in vitro maturation (IVM), buffalos, ovaries oocytes.*

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Introduction

Since the beginning of the history in Iraq, The buffalo has been considered one of the animals whose existence was linked to the presence of the marshes, and they have become one of its distinctive signs for thousands of years. The archaeological drawings discovered depict us as

the buffalo wrestling with a buffalo. With the passage of time, the Sumerians were able to domesticate this animal, which was once wild. Five thousand years ago, it was the companion and dearest friend of the people of the East in general and the Iraqis in particular (Youssef, 2014).

The domestic water buffalo (*Bubalus bubalis*) is important in the agricultural economy of many developing countries in Asia, providing meat, milk and draft power. It is also used in some Latin American and Mediterranean countries as a source of meat and milk for local markets. (Gautam *et al.*,2017).

Although buffalo can adapt to harsh environments and feed on poor quality fodder, reproductive efficiency is often compromised by these conditions, resulting in delayed sexual maturity, poor expression of estrus, prolonged postpartum estrus, and poor pregnancy rates and calving intervals. Age at puberty is affected by genotype, nutrition, management, and climate. Under ideal conditions, estrus occurs at 15-18 months in river buffalo and 21-24 months in swamp buffalo (Wanapat and Rowlinson, 2007).

Polycystic ovary disease in buffaloes is generally divided into three types, including luteal fibrosis, which is fibrosis in the wall of the dominant follicles, or follicular cyst, which occurs in mature ovarian follicles. As for cysts in the tissue of the corpora lutea, then it is called cystic corpora lutea, and it is a non-pathological condition (Teshome *et al.*, 2016).

The current study aimed to demonstrate the effect of nitric oxide and the cumulus cells on the percentage of in vitro maturation (IVM) of buffalos normal ovaries oocytes.

Materials and Methods

Ovaries

Two hundred and eighty buffaloes ovaries were evaluated from the types of polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) used. The source of buffalo eggs were ovaries obtained from the local Al-Muthanna slaughterhouse and the local Najaf slaughterhouse immediately after slaughtering the animals. The ovaries were diagnosed other, or presence of a follicular cyst, or presence of by a corpus luteum cyst.

Collection and Classification of the Buffalo Ovaries and Oocytes

Buffalo ovaries were collected from the local slaughterhouse in Muthanna and the local slaughterhouse in Najaf immediately after slaughtering the animals and placed in plastic containing a normal saline solution (0.9% sodium chloride) supplemented with antibiotics (100 IU/mL penicillin and 100 µg/mL streptomycin). Then it was placed. In a thermos at a temperature of 30-35 ° C. The ovaries were transferred to the laboratory of the College of Agriculture and the laboratory of the College of Medicine, Jabir Bin Hayyan Medical University, within less than 1-1.5 hours. In vitro, ovaries (panel 1) were washed three times with warm normal saline (37°C) described above to remove coagulation and reduce contamination on the surface of the ovaries (Rizk, 2009).

Figure 1. Buffalo Ovaries after Washing

The condition of the ovaries is diagnosed as normal or as having PCOS, which is classified

according to the type of PCOS (cystic corpus luteum or cystic corpus luteum). Oocytes were

collected from all follicles visible on the ovarian surface with a diameter greater than 2 mm using an aspiration technique. Oocytes with follicular fluid were aspirated using a 20-gauge hypodermic needle attached to a sterile disposable syringe containing 0.5 mL of SMART medium supplemented with 20 IU/mL heparin to prevent coagulation of the follicular fluid. After oocyte retrieval, the content of each injection was poured into a Petri dish. This content was then examined under a dissecting microscope to collect eggs using a modified pasture pipette and washed for three times with SMART medium (DeSmedt et al., 1992).

Classification of Oocytes

After collection, oocytes were washed three times using SMART medium, they were counted and classified under inverted microscope into immature, mature and atretic oocytes according to presence of 1st polar body and some morphological features of oocytes (Nogueira et al., 2009; Cavilla et al., 2008).

In vitro Maturation (IVM)

The oocytes were washed using SMART containing 5% HSA to remove substances in follicular fluid. The immature oocytes were directly distributed in average of 5 oocytes per droplet (0.5mL) from Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM), supplied with 10 IU/mL hCG, 5 IU/mL PMSG and 1µg/mL estradiol and cultured in four well dish and covered with liquid paraffin, then incubated for 24 h in CO₂ incubator (5% CO₂) at 38.5°C with 100% humidity.

Results

The result table (1) shows a non-significant differences between the treatments of nitric oxide concentration (low and high) and the presence of cumulus cells on the percentage of IVM of buffalo oocytes.

On the other hand the result table (2) shows a highly-significant ($P \leq 0.01$) differences between the treatments of nitric oxide concentration (low and high) and the presence of cumulus cells on the percentage of IVM of buffalo oocytes. The treatment low concentration of nitric oxide records a highest percentage of IVM in the

oocytes with cumulus cells was $74.50 \pm 2.94 \%$ and the lowest percentage was recorded in the control treatment (without nitric oxide) was $53.50 \pm 1.31\%$ and the treatment of high concentration of nitric oxide an cumulus cells was $53.50 \pm 3.64 \%$.

Table 1. The Effect of Nitric Oxide and the Cumulus Cells on the Percentage of In Vitro Maturation (IVM) of Buffalos Normal Ovaries Oocytes

Treatment	No.	IVM (%)± standard error
control	20	4.32± 64.50
Low NO + CC	20	3.10± 68.50
High NO + CC	20	3.10± 67.00
Low NO. without CC	20	4.99± 66.00
High NO. without CC	20	3.73± 74.50
significant	---	NS
NS :Insignificant.		

Note: low Nitric Oxide + cumulus, High Nitric Oxide + cumulus, low Nitric Oxide. without cumulus, High Nitric Oxide without cumulus

Table 2. The Effect of Nitric Oxide and the Cumulus Cells on the Percentage of In Vitro Maturation (IVM) of Buffalos Cystic Ovaries Oocytes

Treatment	No.	IVM ± standard error %
Control	20	1.31± 53.50b
Low NO+ CC	20	2.94± 74.50a
High NO + CC	20	3.64± 53.50b
Low NO. without CC	20	4.16± 69.00a
High NO. without CC	20	2.10± 56.00b
significant	---	**
Averages with different letters within one column differ significantly from each other. **($P \leq 0.01$).		

Note: low Nitric Oxide + cumulus, High Nitric Oxide + cumulus, low Nitric Oxide. without cumulus, High Nitric Oxide without cumulus

Table (3) shows a significant ($P \leq 0.05$) differences between the normal & cystic ovaries in the control treatment in the percentage of laboratory maturation, wherein the cystic ovaries records a low percentage of laboratory maturation $53.50 \pm 1.31\%$ as compared with the

normal ovaries $64.50 \pm 4.32\%$, while treatments of low concentrations of nitric oxide records a non-significant differences in the percentage of laboratory maturation both in case with presence or non-presence of cumulus cells whereas the treatment of high concentration of nitric oxide records a highly-significant ($P \leq 0.01$) differences between the normal & cystic ovaries in the percentage of laboratory maturation wherein the normal ovaries records a highly percentage of laboratory maturation $67.00 \pm 3.11\%$ as compared with the cystic ovaries $53.50 \pm 3.64\%$ with presence of cumulus cells and the normal ovaries records a highly percentage of laboratory maturation $74.50 \pm 3.73\%$ as compared with the cystic ovaries $56.00 \pm 2.10\%$ without the cumulus cells.

Table 3. The Correlation between the Normal & Cystic Ovaries in the Percentage of Laboratory Maturation

Treatment	IVM \pm standard error %		Sig.
	Natural ovaries	Polycystic ovaries	
control	4.32 \pm 64.50	1.31 \pm 53.50	*
Low NO + CC	3.10 \pm 68.50	2.94 \pm 74.50	NS
High NO + CC	3.10 \pm 67.00	3.64 \pm 53.50	**
Low NO .without CC	4.99 \pm 66.00	4.16 \pm 69.00	NS
High NO .without CC	3.73 \pm 74.50	2.10 \pm 56.00	**
(* $P \leq 0.05$) ** ,($P \leq 0.01$).			

Note: low Nitric Oxide + cumulus, High Nitric Oxide + cumulus, low Nitric Oxide. without cumulus, High Nitric Oxide without cumulus

Discussion

The reproductive efficiency of buffalo is relatively poor regardless of their location throughout the world. Buffalo exhibit several well-known reproductive problems including delayed onset of puberty, poor onset of estrus, ovarian inactivity for a longer period after birth, and most importantly, lower pregnancy rates, especially when raised in pens (Gordon, 2002). The buffalo fertility can be achieved by improving management and nutrition (Qureshi *et al.*, 2007).

The reproductive fitness of buffalo species is determined by many different processes, which result from the interaction between genetics and environment, it includes the age of puberty or maturity, the form of the estrus period and the behavior during the estrus, the rate of ovulation, the lactation period, the period of postpartum estrus, the period between births, and the duration of reproductive life, a combination of these traits is used to characterize breeding efficiency in farm animals (Agrawal, 2003).

Conclusion

The polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS) in general is a dysfunction of the ovaries of livestock, which causes reproductive failure, prolonging the period between two births, and raising production costs, which led to major economic losses for livestock breeders. It is characterized by the presence of permanent follicular or luteinized structures on the ovaries (Vanholder, 2006; Rose, 2012).

The hormonal disorders causing polycystic ovary syndrome. Although there is a wide range of studies that have addressed the biological mechanisms of polycystic ovary syndrome, the exact causes of its occurrence are still unknown (Peter, 2004; Vanholder, *et al.*; 2006).

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